
Organic Livestock Production

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The concept of organic farming is not novel; people of India and the world were using natural agricultural products from the soil without using any chemical fertilizers. The farmers were growing the fodder crops and feeding to animals without any chemical residue in the body of animals subsequently in animal products like milk, meat, wool, egg, etc. The need for organic farming is the real essence of the current era to reduce the harmful effects of various chemicals in humans. Agriculture and livestock organic production can run parallel to each other but livestock products will be last to be certified as organic. The farmers are aware of the benefits offered by organic farming as well as the hazards of synthetic chemicals in farming. They are also well aware that it will curb pollution levels in the environment and be eco-friendly. Organic livestock farming generally means raising livestock on organic feed (i.e. pastures cultivated without the use of fertilizers or pesticides), having access to pasture or outside, along with the restricted usage of antibiotics and hormones (Oruganti, 2011). Organic farming should not include or strictly limits the use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, antibiotics, feed additives, and GMOs. The products like milk, meat, eggs, etc. obtained from livestock reared on organic farmland, given natural organic feed and routine health monitoring. The products so obtained will attain an organic tag in the market, leading to fetch more prices from buyers. Cow urine has a unique function and ability to be used as a pest repellent and growth promoter. The better utilization of waste matter from the organic livestock allows farmers to reduce their dependence on synthetic or chemical soil amendments from outside and thus, curb other extra costs.

Basic Requirements

To get valid Organic certification, livestock farmers must follow the guidelines mentioned below:

1. Animals must be managed in a way that conserves natural resources on farm and biodiversity.

2. No antibiotics or artificial growth hormones are totally prohibited.
3. The livestock feed must be 100% certified organic and animals must be raised on certified organic land.
4. Animals must have year-round access to the outdoors for grazing.

Advantages of Organic Livestock Production

Livestock manure and compost helps in the nutrient utilization and recycling process by which nutrients are returned to the soil through excreta. Amending the soil nutrients with animal manures can increase microbial population and biomass, enzymatic activity, and alter the structure of the microbial fauna. The incorporation of feed crops, such as berseem or grasses into crop rotations helps to build organic matter in the soil. Livestock also contributes to controlling weeds by grazing animals on weeds. Change in the cropping options in the field results in adding diversity to the agro-ecosystem. Livestock such as bullock can plough new land before planting vegetables or grains, reducing tillage and weed control costs. Livestock grazing breaks the insect and disease cycles by taking land out of cropping. Livestock incorporates value to grazing lands and promotes the use of green manures. Reducing the financial cost of fertilizers as well as risks of farming by converting lower quality grain crops into profit and spreading income over the years.

Organic grassland

The Organic grassland for grazing animals is the first demand and foundation stone of pure organic livestock farming. In organic farming, grassland plays a central role in this farming in which all the components interact with each other, including the arable cropping phase. Ruminant livestock plays a central role with grassland on most successful organic farms.

Requisite for organic livestock production

Livestock

The livestock must fulfill the condition that any livestock and its products (milk, meat, egg, etc.) from the livestock that is sold in the market, labeled, or advertised as the organic product must be from livestock that originates from animals that were managed under continuous organic farming management from the last third of gestation or at hatching. Organic cows are grazed on pastures that are grown through organic means. Therefore, their milk is not contaminated with harmful chemicals such as the residues of pesticides, fertilizers, and hormones (Singh et al. 2011).

Livestock Feed

Livestock ration is comprised of agricultural products including pasture, forage, and crops that are organically produced on agriculture farms. Dairy cattle under 9 months of age are allowed 20% of their feed comes from non-organic sources. The use of plastic pellets, urea, manure, mammalian or poultry slaughter by-products is not allowed.

Housing Conditions

The livestock must be kept in well-managed climatic conditions with maximum welfare. The living conditions in the shed must include access to outdoors or runs, shade, clean shelter, fresh air, direct sunlight suitable to the species, and access to pasture for grazing ruminants.

Organic manure and organic matter

The farmer on integrated livestock will have an extra advantage in organic farming as they never need to purchase extra soil-incorporation materials because of fact that livestock waste can be utilized as simply as manure or natural fertilizer on the farm for promoting fodder growth. It is eco-friendly; farm-based animal manures could help in successful organic farming.

It improves soil structure, quality and leads to increased water infiltration, better water-holding capacity, and good nutrient retention in soil. The good effect was also seen on cation exchange capacity and soil pH.

Waste Management

Organic livestock producers are required to manage manure so that it does not contribute to the contamination of crops, soil, or water through pollutants and optimizes the efficiency of recycling nutrients.

Health Care and management

The health care practices must be appropriate including selecting the appropriate species and type of livestock, providing adequate feed, create an appropriate environment. It must minimize stress, disease, parasites, and its eggs, administration of vaccines and veterinary biologicals, husbandry practices to promote health and wellbeing in a manner that minimizes pain, suffering, and stress to animals.

Stadlbauer *et al.* (2013) reported that 78.00 percent herd vaccinating and using veterinarian in the conventional head, whereas in organic herd only 30.00 percent herd vaccinating and using veterinarian. Zwald *et al.* (2004) reported that above 90.00 percent of

organic herd was not received at least single dose of antibiotics, whereas in nearly 95.00 percent conventional herd was received at least a single dose of antibiotics

Record Keeping/audit Trail

Organic livestock operations need to maintain records for a number of reasons at livestock farms. Records are very important to verify the organic status of animals, production systems, and handling practices related to organic products. Records are maintained at least for five years and must demonstrate compliance with the Organic Food Production act.

Dairy production

The livestock Feed must be fed to animals having 100% organic feed for one year. Antibiotics should be prohibited for 1 year prior to milking of animals. There is a prohibition on the use of hormones except for oxytocin before one year of milking and after organic certification. Approved vaccines in animals can be used for controlling the disease. Pasture must have access to organic pasture.

Poultry production (Meat and Eggs)

The conditions in poultry are almost similar. The poultry Feed must be 100% organic feed from the second day of life. Antibiotics and Hormones are entirely prohibited but vaccines and other biologics must be used which are approved as needed. Poultry must have an extensive rearing system and be given free access to the outdoors.

Slaughter Livestock (Beef, Hogs, Sheep, etc.)

The feed of livestock must be 100% organic feed from the last third of gestation. antibiotics and Hormones are prohibited except for oxytocin. Organic farms are required to use the approved vaccines and biologics as needed. Animals must have access to the outdoors and Organic pasture is required for ruminant livestock.

Problems in developing organic animal husbandry

Many tropical countries are making consistent efforts to boost organic farming, especially of high-value commercial crops, and got success but there are some serious problems and challenges that are still circumscribing growth in organic farming. Some of these potential problems/ obstacles are as follows:

- lack of knowledge
- small farms

- problems in livestock feeding
- sanitary regulations
- traceability
- disease
- lack of training and certification facilities.

Organic certification in India

The National Standards for Organic Products was framed in 2000 which certifies the genuineness of the organic products. The certification is provided by testing centres that are recognized by the *agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development authority (aPEDa)*. The certification board was established in 2000 but the scheme came into existence in the year 2002 which provides the mark to the organic products in a real sense.

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